

ПОЛИТИЧЕСКАЯ ЭКОНОМИЯ И ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ПОЛИТИКА: ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ COVID-19

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PANDEMIC AND CAPITAL³: COVID-19 REPERCUSSIONS ON SOCIAL REPRODUCTION IN BRAZIL

Keywords: COVID-19, Coronavirus, Public health, Pandemic, Epidemiology, Marxism, Brazil.

Расширенная аннотация статьи на русском языке¹

Авторы статьи ставят перед собой цель систематизировать основания для онтологического осмысления пандемии Covid-19 и ее последствий для социального воспроизводства в Бразилии. Выдвигается положение о био-социальном характере заболеваний, которые исторически поражали человечество. В статье кратко охарактеризованы несколько основных эпидемий, которые были зафиксированы в истории. С давних пор и до нашего времени эти вспышки оказы-

вали сильное воздействие на отношения между государствами, они влияли на исходы войн, вносили коррективы в социальное устройство обществ.

В Бразилии пандемия в основном затронула рабочих и представителей низших классов. Для миллионов бразильцев, которые уже были безработными или работали нелегально в теневом секторе экономики, ситуация еще больше усложнялась по мере распространения вируса и с введением сдерживающих его мер. Многим пришлось выбирать между риском заражения и голодом. Особенно из-за неспособности и отказа правительства принять эффективные меры защиты.

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³ Capital is understood here as a social relation of production, in which all productive forces of a given society are directed towards the production of value. In the specific case of the capitalist society, we simply call it profit. Most of the scientific and productive effort ultimately aims at capital accumulation.

Помимо умозаключений качественного характера, авторы стремятся использовать эмпирические методы для оценки воздействия Covid-19 на исторически угнетенные группы населения, такие как коренные народы Бразилии. Делается вывод, что последствия зависимого капитализма и текущего кризиса капитала стали намного более острыми после широкого распространения пандемии.

Авторы основывают свой анализ на формулировках К. Маркса, Д. Лукача и И. Месароша о «гуманизме природы и натурализме человека» (Маркс), о человеке как социальном существе, и природе как его неотъемлемой основе. В то же время обмен между природой и обществом подразумевает постоянное взаимодействие между естественными причинно-следственными связями и причинностью как синтезом телеологических постулатов, продвигаемых людьми. Таким образом, мы исходим из того, что ситуации, связанные со здоровьем и болезнями, нельзя интерпретировать только с биологической и медицинской точек зрения. Помимо биологических, причинами развития и последствий пандемии являются различные социальные факторы. Эти факторы, как утверждается в статье, тесно связаны с капиталистическим способом производства и его национальными особенностями. Авторы исследуют связь между эпидемией (как биологическим явлением) и общественно-производственными отношениями через призму марксизма с целью определить возможные пути изучения появ-

ления, распространения и последствий Covid-19 на основе исторического анализа социально-экономических процессов.

В этом ключе главным основанием для авторов является работа Р. Уоллеса, которая связывает участвовавшее возникновение пандемий с крупномасштабной монокультурной сельскохозяйственной моделью, господствующей во всем мире. Согласно этому аргументу, интенсивная концентрация животных на промышленных фермах агробизнеса способствовала появлению высокопатогенных штаммов вирусов.

В заключение авторы приходят к выводу, что для эффективной борьбы с Covid-19 необходимы решительные меры в области здравоохранения, жилищно-коммунального хозяйства, социальной помощи, санитарии и др. Но, по сути, необходимо создать новую, нехищническую общественную систему, способную смягчить последствия естественных причинно-следственных связей посредством планового и рационального производства и воспроизводства. Трансформация производственных отношений, нацеленная на переориентацию прогресса производительных сил и, следовательно, переориентация государственных инвестиций на решение проблем здравоохранения всех, даже с реформистской точки зрения, в конечном итоге оказывается единственным выходом из положения в кратко- и среднесрочном периоде для человечества.

Основной текст статьи

Introduction

Pandemics are here since the dawn of mankind. History records the most diverse

diseases, epidemics and pandemics which in certain historical particularities and situations have afflicted tribes, communities,

towns, cities and entire nations. Pandemics are a striking remind of the irrepressible bond between the human being and nature, which is naturally human and humanly natural {Citation}.

The diseases, with great capacity for dissemination and contagion, have devastated even the most fortified cities, as was the case with the Anthonina plague that struck Rome in 165. The pandemic that occurred in the Roman Empire began with the troops that were installed in the Parthia, a Roman territory located in Mesopotamia. Through these troops, the disease arrived in Rome in 166 and was the cause of up to two thousand deaths a day {Citation}. Studies indicate it was probably an outbreak of smallpox. It is estimated that 5 million people died as a result of the Anthonina plague.

Throughout the history and birth of modern society, we can highlight some diseases that have become epidemics and, in some cases, pandemics. In chronological order we can highlight: Plague of Athens (430-427 BC.); Anthonina plague in Rome (166); smallpox epidemic in Japan (735-737); Bubonic plague (1347-1353); China plague (1641); yellow fever epidemic in New Orleans (1853); cholera pandemics (throughout the 19th century); Spanish flu (1918-1919); AIDS pandemic (1980); SARS-1 pandemic (2002-2004); Swine flu (2009); Cholera epidemic in Haiti (2010); Ebola (2013-2016); Zika virus (2015); Covid-19 pandemic (2020).

Pandemics have destroyed even armies, such as in the case of the Spanish flu (1918/19) that occurred during the First World War (1914-1918), causing the death of approximately 50 million people in all parts of the planet {Citation}. The global impact of the Spanish flu is estimated to have killed 1 to 3% of humanity. In the middle of the war, the flu found a favorable place in armies' campsites and in the trenches

of the battlefield, leading to the death of many soldiers. This became an important factor in the battle of empires {Citation}. In the Global South countries, the Spanish flu had different repercussions:

It is rarely appreciated that a large proportion of global mortality has occurred in Punjab, Mumbai and other parts of West India, where cereal exports to Britain and brutal export practices have coincided with a major drought. The resulting food shortages brought dozens of poor people to the brink of starvation. They became victims of a sinister synergy between malnutrition - which suppressed their immune response to infection and produced bacterial inflammation as well as viral pneumonia {Citation}

Pandemics are not casual events in history. They are essentially social events which are destructive and lethal to what extent each particular societal formation is prepared and resolved to deal with them. Even in the contemporary times, because science cannot immediately decode them, let alone deal with them in the heat of their outbreak. They are part of a social-natural chain of causalities and the discovery of a new highly infectious virus, including the different possible treatments and vaccines, require time for scientific research.² By its own, a virus is nothing more than a virus. It is only when in touch with other living beings that a virus becomes a disease, a syndrome or, when connected to highly complex societies, it might become a pandemic. The Marxist philosopher György Lukács (2009) argues that causality functions as a "spontaneous law in which all the movements of all forms of being find their general expression." In this sense, it is wrong to forcibly separate the binomial health and disease as purely natural and biological phenomena from their intimate social connection.

² As Lukács (2009) points, knowledge is always a *post festum* ideal reconstruction of reality.

The diseases that devastated humanity in the most diverse regions of the world had repercussions and results that, in one way or another, brought about significant changes in social reproduction. Some diseases favored colonialism and imperialist invasions, changing the geopolitics of the world. Measles, influenza, bubonic plague, malaria, diphtheria, typhus, cholera and, above all, smallpox made possible the near extermination of the native peoples of America after the arrival of the Europeans. The population of South America was reduced from 60 million people (about 10% of the world's population in the 15th century) to only 6 million in a little more than a hundred years. On Alencastro's (2000) study on the national formation of Brazil, is emphasized that the microbial unification of the world by Europeans and the vulnerability of indigenous peoples to epidemiological shock were factors that constrained native captivity and, conversely, facilitated the increase of black slavery:

Carried by vessels coming from Lisbon, smallpox (smallpox major, the only of the three types of disease existing at the time) infected Bahia in 1562, when a "pestilential corruption" killed three quarters of the village indigenous people. The disease then spread to the North, through Pernambuco, and to the South, through Piratinga. There were outbreaks in various parts of the Portuguese world, so the missionaries signed at the same time a "universal pox disease" that invaded Japan. The Brazilian ports suffered from the contagion of the variolic waves that broke out in Portugal between 1597 and 1616. The same relationship between morbidity and mortality must have occurred in Portuguese America as in the native communities on the other side of the Andes: 30% to 50% of the Indians exposed to the disease died in the first days (Alencastro 2000, 123).

In contrast, yellow fever and the slave revolt in Haiti were together major obstacles to French rule and Napoleon Bonaparte's projects in North America. During the Haitian Revolution, yellow fever devastated Napoleon's soldiers, about 50,000 soldiers, officers, doctors and sailors died in Haiti in the late 18th and early 19th centuries {Citation}.

The African continent also suffered from a plague that favored European colonial expansion. Between 1888 and 1897, the rinderpest virus killed 90% of Africa's livestock, leaving communities devastated in Southeast Africa, West Africa and the Southwest of the continent. The loss of the herd led to hunger and forced the migration of local people. The chaos generated by the disease facilitated European colonization in large areas of Africa in the late 19th century. By the 1870s, only about 10% of Africa was under European control, but by 1900 that number had risen to about 90% {Citation}.

After briefly summarizing some historical events involving diseases that have become epidemics or pandemics, we note that they do not fail to influence the economy, politics, culture and social relations, even in smaller degrees. A pandemic hardly ceases to affect the living conditions of the impinged societies. In the case of Covid-19 (coronavirus - SARS-CoV-2), a disease that had its first records at the end of 2019 and, therefore, its proliferation and global consequences occurred in the year 2020, the repercussions on the global and Brazilian working class are significant and accentuated the already precarious living conditions of millions.

Coronavirus (Covid-19) and its repercussion on social reproduction

The coronavirus (Covid-19) can cause fever, breathing difficulties and cough, in some cases it can resemble a flu. The

contagion of Covid-19 occurs through respiratory droplets, and the best measure found to prevent it is social isolation, which avoids crowding. The first cases of the disease allegedly occurred in late 2019 in the city of Wuhan, Hubei province, People's Republic of China.³ The World Health Organization (WHO) declared on January 30, 2020 that the outbreak of the disease (Covid-19), caused by the new coronavirus, constitutes a public health emergency of international importance, the highest level of WHO's alert, as set forth in the International Health Regulations. On March 11, 2020, Covid-19 was characterized by WHO as a pandemic. By July 11, 2020, the day this article was drafted, 12.507.849 cases have been confirmed worldwide and 560.460 deaths. Brazil is one of the countries with community transmission and has confirmed 1.804.338 cases and 70.524 deaths from the disease (OPAS and OMS 2020)

Unfortunately, the outcome of the coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic is catastrophic. The right to life was relativized in many countries, even though some of them had to include temporarily in their agendas measures to protect the people and allocate resources to combat the coronavirus (Covid-19) and mitigate its disastrous impact. The economic and political consequences of these measures are still ongoing, but one of the few certainties is that the post-pandemic world will also be one of intensification of the capitalist crisis already underway before and redesign of geopolitics. The virus may not choose the social class, but the material conditions that each class or segment of class have available to face these trying times are

unequal and unbalanced. The subaltern classes are the most affected and, in Brazil, workers have to choose between being at risk of contagion and starvation. When the unemployed, slum dwellers, homeless, quilombola communities, indigenous tribes and informal workers do not die from the disease, they find the greatest difficulties in medical assistance and in the policies to confront the health crisis.

Most of the urban population encounters great difficulties and literally does not present adequate conditions of social isolation, since they live in crowded cottages with limited number of rooms, only rest after a long and strenuous working day, in most cases in the informal economy. There are 11,5 million people in Brazil living in overpopulated domiciles with three or more persons per room, most of them are black or brown (FOLHAPRESS 2020). This situation is different from that observed in the privileged class, which can choose how to work, when to work and in which conditions to practice social isolation to face the pandemic. Many privileged people may even go to their country houses and let the cauldron boil in the big metropolises. Certainly money still cannot buy immunity, but it can provide adequate social isolation and good treatment.

One fundamental issue to take into consideration while we approach this problem through the Marxist paradigm of reciprocity between men and nature is that the health of the individual and the health of the whole society are not separated, especially as cities are organized:

Both the spread of the virus responsible for this pandemic and the unevenly effective measures taken by states to protect their populations prove, if necessary, that health is first and foremost a public good: that the healthy or morbid state of each person's body depends first and foremost on the healthy or morbid state of the

³ Recent discoveries of the new coronavirus in sewage samples in four different countries, including Brazil, until months before the Wuhan outbreak, raise further questions about the origin and current evolutionary chronology of the pandemic {Citation}.

social body, on which the former is dependent or a mere appendage, and on the ability or otherwise of that body to defend itself or through its political institutions against pathogenic factors, in particular by developing an efficient welfare system and a public health policy that provides the latter with the necessary and sufficient means (human, material, financial) (Bihl 2020, 25).

It is worth remembering that many working-class segments did not stop working at Covid-19 and many received their own death as payment for their efforts, an example of this are the health professionals. Many workers have no choice, they need to go to the front in the war against the pandemic, because hospitals, funeral homes, logistics, cleaning and sanitation, supermarkets, meat processing, agriculture cannot stop functioning to maintain the survival of the population.

Several analyses have been and will be produced to explain the origin of the coronavirus pandemic. We have evaluated that establishing a relationship between epidemiology and production relationships, as a study hypothesis, may be a heuristic tool to get closer to the socioeconomic understanding of this pandemic. Even so, we recognize that there is a long way to go for science to reach an accurate conclusion on the origin of Covid-19 and its various forms of dissemination and how to successfully suppress it.

Dialectic coexistence - between health and society (relations of production) - needs to be considered in the analysis of diseases, in the same way that we have already highlighted that the health of the individual and the health of society coexist. We understand that it is not only isolated biological and/or natural processes that produce disease, but all social relations involved in the production and reproduction of life (biological and social) under

certain historical conditions. Of course, we cannot perform analyses based on hierarchical and deterministic factors, but if we do not inquire what sort of society that is producing the disease, our answer will hardly have historical validity. We have to overcome the view that the disease is an individual's disease. Diseases result from socio-epidemiological processes (Breilh 2020).

Regarding Covid-19, among several historical analyses that speculate its origin, we have some evidence that its emergence, when analyzed not in isolation to the mark zero of the wet market in the city of Wuhan, may be related to the hegemonic agricultural model (RBA 2020).

Some articles that dialogue with critics of the political economy were produced by internationally known authors from the academic universe (Mike Davis 2020, Foster n.d., 2020, Harvey 2020, Žižek 2020), as well as gaining prominence in autonomous editorials such as the Chinese collective Chuang (n.d.) which, in our evaluation, presented interesting analysis based on economic data and dialogue with important theoretical productions such as the book *Big Farms Make Big Flu: Dispatches on infectious disease, agribusiness, and the nature of Science*, by biologist Robert Wallace (2016).

After reading the work of the Chuang (n.d.) collective, we understand that possible scenarios need to be taken into consideration: 1) unfortunately, humanity is seeing the outcome of its food production choices with intensive use of pesticides; 2) [intensive production and animal husbandry (industrial farms) provide perfect conditions for the emergence of highly pathogenic viral strains;⁴ 3) this mode of

⁴ We quote here Paim and Alonso's explanations about the pathogens and their relations with the intensive livestock farms for human consumption: "There are many types of influenza viruses circulating

production engenders radically the mutations of the global climate system and microbiological substrates of life on Earth; 4) housing conditions and insalubrity provide, with ease, the spread of diseases that become pandemics in the globally connected world in which we live.⁵ It is clear that these conclusions cannot be analysed in isolation, as we would run the risk of being accused of social Darwinism. However, what we propose is a reflection to question the origin of diseases and how they

in wild animals, mostly waterfowl. Their transmission to humans from these species is not a trivial task. Many essential mutations are necessary so that viruses that reproduce in the digestive system of birds, and that are carried by water, can effectively be transmitted by air and infect the human respiratory system. The perfect conditions for the selection and propagation of the mutations that have enabled contamination and efficient propagation in humans are present in the intermediate hosts between waterfowl and humans: the chickens and pigs we raise for consumption. The high density and large number of animals kept on intensive farming facilities, where most of the chicken and pork meat sold to the population is produced, has allowed the mixing of different strains of avian influenza and the combination of their genetic material (a process called 'antigenic change'), which has repeatedly led to the emergence of viruses that can also infect humans. Pigs are particularly suitable as intermediate hosts for these viruses, as their upper respiratory tract contains receptors for both the avian influenza virus (SA-alpha-2.3) and the pig/human virus (SA-alpha-2.6). Intensive animal husbandry systems, also known as industrial farms, have created the perfect environment for the emergence of highly pathogenic viral strains, along with the ideal medium for human infection" (Paim and Alonso 2020, 22).

⁵ The world today is interconnected, mainly by the third dynamic and historical complex analyzed by Lukács (2013). The Hungarian philosopher, when studying the production and reproduction of life, considers three great dynamic and historical complexes that develop uninterruptedly in the course of humanity's evolution. The first is the decrease in the amount of labor needed for the physical reproduction of man; the second is the retreat of natural barriers through the command of labor and the growing socialization of society (and nature); the third, in turn, is the growing integration among societies that are in reciprocal relationship by the world market.

are produced, as we know that nature and humanity coexist reciprocally, keeping their particularities, as a product and producer in a constant dialectic relationship.⁶ For this reason, "the natural world, including the microbiological substrate, cannot be understood without reference to how society organizes production (because the two are not, in fact, separated) (Chuang n.d.)."

Social production, the way in which human beings produce and reproduce their existences, is always mediated by a given historical form of society, for "all production is the appropriation of nature by the individual within and mediated by a certain form of society" (Marx 2011, 43). To understand production as humanity's inevitable (and dialectic) relationship with nature (naturalized man and humanized nature) and to analyze human praxis as ongoing (not total) removals of natural barriers is to propose an understanding of production (whether of commodities and/or pandemics) in its respective socio-historical context.

In the aforementioned document from the Chuang collective, we draw attention to the sub-item in which "The production of plagues" is addressed. Below we transcribe one of the main passages of the document with the purpose of exposing a crucial argument of this work:

The virus behind the present epidemic (SARS-CoV-2), was, like its 2003 predecessor

⁶ "Long ago I had rejected the idea of 'nature' as alien and separate from culture, economy and everyday life. I have a more dialectical and relational view of the metabolic connection with nature. Capital modifies the environmental conditions of its own reproduction, but it does so in a context of unintended consequences (such as climate change) and against the autonomous and independent evolutionary forces that are perpetually reshaping environmental conditions. From this point of view, there is no real natural disaster. Viruses change all the time. But the circumstances in which a mutation becomes a threat to life depend on human actions." (Harvey 2020, 15)

sor SARS-CoV, as well as the avian flu and swine flu before it, gestated at the nexus of economics and epidemiology. It's not coincidental that so many of these viruses have taken on the names of animals: The spread of new diseases to the human population is almost always the product of what's called zoonotic transfer, which is a technical way of saying that such infections jump from animals to humans. [...] The basic idea here is developed most thoroughly by left-wing biologists like Robert G. Wallace whose 2016 book *Big Farms Make Big Flu* makes an exhaustive case for the connection between capitalist agribusiness and the etiology of recent epidemics ranging from SARS to Ebola. (Chuang n.d.)

The above argument gains importance for understanding pandemics in a world where mass and unscrupulous production of food with no healthy nutrition is highly accelerated by the demands of competitiveness and productivity of agricultural companies, always aiming for the maximum possible profit. Eating poisoned meals and junk food is the only possible choice for the majority of the population. Wallace's (2016)⁷ research shows that the origin of new viruses results from the intense penetration of agribusiness in nature and its natural microbiological systems, creating cracks in ecosystems and animal species, which can allow the emergence of possible global pandemics. For this reason, it is important to bring explanations such as those presented by Wallace (2016) and Chuang (n.d.). According to Foster (2020), it is worth understanding that this

"ecological and epidemiological criticism" is not new. The young Engels dealt extensively with diseases and epidemiological conditions at the time of the Industrial Revolution, particularly in his study that resulted in the seminal book *The Situation of the Working Class in England*, published originally in 1845. Engels denounced the "social murder" caused by diseases and epidemics, mainly by working conditions, housing, food, health and life of the proletariat.

For two centuries, therefore, there has been a causal relationship between environments and circumstances with high proliferation of diseases and the capitalist mode of production. Under capitalism, labor is impregnated with alienating social complexes that deform it as an ontological creative activity: wage-earning labor takes on an animalizing and degrading dimension, is unhealthy and dangerous (Marx 2010, 83–84). In short, there is no possibility of a healthy society with a structure whose production relations are based on labor exploitation. Even countries with so-called welfare states have suffered great setbacks and show that social reforms are insufficient, partial or temporary and that without changing standards of production and social reproduction pandemics like this can become routine.

It is also necessary to criticize the beneficiaries of the diseases: the pharmaceutical industry. Harvey (2020, 18) is shrewd in his analysis which argues that "the pharmaceutical industry has little or no interest in non-profit research on infectious diseases (such as the whole class of coronavirus known since the 1960s). We know that the pharmaceutical industry rarely invests in prevention, let alone is interested in preparing for a public health and health crisis like pandemics. Prevention does not contribute to shareholder value on the stock markets. The survival and health of the

⁷ The Monthly Review Editorial (2020) takes up the debate presented by Wallace (2016) and recalls the role of agribusiness, ecological degradation and emerging diseases that become global pandemics. In *The Great Bird Flu Blame Game* chapter of the aforementioned book, Wallace explains that the whole structure of agribusiness needed to be confronted if these emerging pandemics are to be stopped:

lower classes will never have priority over the profits of the pharmaceutical industry in capitalism. According to Davis (2020), in the current Covid-19 pandemic, capitalist production is biologically unsustainable in the absence of a true international public health infrastructure. "But such infrastructure will never exist until popular movements break the power of the pharmaceutical industry and profit-driven healthcare" (Davis 2020, 11).

Fighting the pandemic is not only a challenge itself, but even the more biomedical approaches are finding the neoliberal paradigm as huge obstacles to be surpassed in order to face the virus. This paradigm, in the last decades, has been voracious in fiscal austerity measures and reduction of investments in public policies to the maximum. In the highly integrated societies we live in, the health of the individual and the health of society can never be considered in isolation. The privatist mindset on health, which preaches that each individual can buy "the best health" from the private companies of medical insurance, shipwrecked in contexts of pandemics. States' actions to protect the population prove that health is, first and foremost, a public good (Bihl 2020), and that each individual's healthy or sick condition depends primarily on society's healthy or morbid condition. Society's ability to defend itself against diseases and pandemics depends in fact and on a genuine system of public policies on health, social assistance, housing, labor and basic sanitation.⁸

⁸ "Public authorities and healthcare systems have been caught in almost every place with a shortage of staff. Forty years of neoliberalism in North and South America and Europe had left the public totally exposed and ill-prepared to face such a public health crisis, despite the earlier risks of SARS and Ebola providing abundant warnings as well as convincing lessons on what needed to be done. In many parts of the supposedly 'civilised' world, local governments

The labor market in Brazil today is composed of workers who, in some cases, work 14 hours or more per day. They are the workers without social rights of the most diverse applications such as Uber, Rappi, iFood, domestic workers, peddlers, that is, 40% to 50% of the workers who live in informality or in weakened labor contract (without and legal social protection).⁹ It was these workers who crowded the agencies of the Caixa Econômica Federal¹⁰ seeking the R\$ 600.00 (approximately US\$ 115,00).¹¹ The current versions of the meritocracy and "entrepreneurship" ideologies, as alternatives to regulated employment, were severely affected during the emergence of the pandemic.

It is important to understand that the "elites" national project for Brazil before Covid-19 was already tragic for the lower classes. Social security was criminally attacked, labor social protection was reduced to a minimum by the counter-re-

and regional/state authorities, which invariably form the front line of defence in public health and security emergencies of this kind, had been deprived of funding through an austerity policy aimed at financing tax cuts and subsidies to corporations and the wealthy" (Harvey 2020, 17–18).

⁹ Before the pandemic, the rate of informality in the labor market was 40.6% in the quarter ended in February, totaling 38 million workers (Kitahara 2020).

¹⁰ One of the main state-owned banks in Brazil and the medium of payment for the government's social assistance programs that include monetary payment to the poor.

¹¹ The Emergency Aid is a benefit for informal workers, "individual micro-entrepreneurs" (MEI), the self-employed and the unemployed affected by the pandemic. The benefit in the amount of R\$ 600,00 will be paid for three months, for up to two people from the same family. For families in which the woman is solely responsible for the household expenses, the amount paid monthly will be R\$1,200.00. According to the *Ministry of Citizenship*, approximately 97 million requests were received, of these 50 million Brazilians were considered fit and received the aid. The total value of the transfer was R\$ 35.5 billion (Caixa Econômica Federal n.d.)

forms described above, the labor market was plunged into precariousness (so-called precarious work is a constitutive characteristic of our social formation). Brazilian toilers are being held hostage to a national project that clings to dependence and the maintenance of a dominated-dominant class with its privileges (Bambirra 2013).

The privileged are already presenting their opinions filled with irrationalism and class hatred. Guilherme Benchimol, president and founder of XP Investments, on May 6, said the following:

Following our numbers a little bit, I'd say Brazil is fine. Our curves aren't so exponential yet, we've been flattening out. We'll have a clearer picture in the next two to three weeks. The peak of the disease has already passed when we analyze the middle class, upper middle class. The challenge is that Brazil is a country with many ghettos, many favelas, which makes the whole process difficult (Moura 2020).

It is already well-known that the "elites" and the privileged in Brazil are composed of minorities, but new data can always update and reinforce this assessment. According to the National Household Sample Survey (PNAD), released by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), 50% of the country's population had an average monthly income of only R\$850,00 (around US\$ 160,00) in 2019 (IBGE 2020). Among the richest 1%, this average is R\$ 28.659, 00 (roughly US\$ 5.300,00), or 33.7 times more. When considering all the wealth gross produced in the country, approximately 43% of it was in the hands of the people among the 10% with the highest income. While on the bottom of the social pyramid, the population among the 10% with the lowest income held only 0.8% of the total wealth (Kitahara 2020).

Inequalities in wages, housing and all other basic conditions of social reproduction make Brazil one of the countries with

the worst living standards for the majority of the population. As we discussed above about the polyclassistic character of the Covid-19 pandemic in reaching all social classes and segments, this might be truth in countries with equal conditions of health coverage, housing and basic sanitation. However, in Brazil, where access to these services is precarious and profoundly unequal, Covid-19 is definitely biased. We watch astonished by television or read in the most diverse media the desperate people begging for hospital beds for their relatives. We quote below a report that illustrates the situation of the lower classes and the Covid-19 in the city of São Paulo, in which we see the social class that ends up being more affected by the pandemic:

The district of Brasilândia, in the north area of São Paulo, accounts for the highest number of deaths from the new coronavirus in the city [down to 05/06/2020]. They sum 67, according to a survey released by the city administration. The number is almost ten times higher than the number of deaths in Morumbi (7), a noble neighborhood in the south area, which has the highest number of recorded cases: 332. In Brazil, according to data released by the NGO Rede Nossa São Paulo, the risk factor for covid-19 to be fatal is the address. According to the Municipal Health Secretariat of São Paulo, there was a 45% increase in deaths in the 20 poorest districts of the city (Vespa 2020).

Covid-19 ends up being lethal on the suburbs of the cities, because the few hospital beds, the precarious housing conditions to practice social isolation put the lower class in the front line of contamination and death. The first case of Covid-19's death in Rio de Janeiro tragically illustrates the situation of the Brazilian working class: a maid who traveled 120 kilometers to the house of her employer who recently had returned infected from Italy.

The researchers Bombardi and Nepomuceno (2020) demonstrated that Covid-19 first spread to the largest cities (São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro) due to the international transit of people. Also, the number of inhabitants and population density made the contagion faster, which reveals the pattern of unequal urbanization based on exclusion and harm to human health. The authors also warn, as a hypothesis, that many cases of increased contamination may be related to the lack of appropriate sewage disposal due to the possibility of “fecal-oral” contamination. In this case, the catastrophe may be even greater, since in most of Brazil’s municipalities more than 50% of the population does not have sewage treatment. In 2019, approximately 6.1 million households did not have daily pipe water. Regionally, access to sanitary sewage shows striking inequalities in the country. In the North region, only 27.4% of households were connected to the general sewage system. In the Northeast, this percentage was 47.2%. In the Center-West it reached 60%, in the South it increased to 68,7%, reaching the biggest percentage in the Southeast, with 88,9% of the domiciles with access to the sewage disposal network (Silveira 2020).

Another concern involving parts of the subaltern classes is the one respecting to indigenous peoples who may be contaminated by Covid-19. Historically, as we highlighted at the beginning of this article, indigenous peoples are more susceptible to disease and were almost eliminated from America with the arrival of Europeans in the 16th century. One of the possible explanations for the greater risk of contagion of indigenous peoples is that they have not had the same contact with several viruses as the other non-indigenous populations and are therefore more susceptible to diseases brought from out of their social environment. There are approximately

81,000 indigenous people in the Amazon region who are in a vulnerable situation, which can be aggravated by the distances from their tribes to the urban centers that offer treatment in specialized hospitals to combat Covid-19. The increase in deforestation and illegal mining, in this case, are the main factors of contagion.

Within the global working class we have migrant workers, who in the context of pandemics are the first to suffer from xenophobia, racism and difficult access to health services. Some consequences of Covid-19 are presented to these workers in the restriction of mobility when they are in transit, in reception centres with precarious places, in difficulties in admission procedures and requests for asylum or international protection, in refugee camps that do not offer drinking water, basic sanitation, health care and food. While in precarious and informal employment, in some cases they are forced to continue working despite the health risks.¹² The International Organization for Migration (IOM) is monitoring some situations in Southeast Asia, East Africa and Latin America, where thousands of people are unable to return to their country of origin. The situation of refugees and immigrants in border areas and refugee camps, if it was already worrying, is now dramatic, as the places are being isolated (Vendramini and Conde 2020).

¹² Two Bolivian sewing workshop laborers died as a result of Covid-19 in April 2020 in the São Paulo. We highlight the information of Roque Pattussi, coordinator of the Migrant Support and Pastoral Care Center (Cami): “They felt bad. For lack of information, they arrived late at the hospital, when there was not much else to do. They intubated but could not resist [...] In the poorest sewing workshops, there is no radio or television on to pass the least instruction on the disease. They end up losing their lives for lack of adequate information, he says. They don’t know how to identify the symptoms, when they should go to a Health Clinic [...] By doing the math, we reached 24,000 people in complete informality, who also worked for informal workshops” (Sakamoto 2020).

Finally, it is good to reinforce that many studies of social and human sciences, so discredited in the current context, are fundamental to understand the size of the problem we are facing, because to combat Covid-19, vigorous policies of health, housing, social assistance, sanitation among others are needed. But fundamentally, a new non-predatory social metabolic system needs to be established without opposition to nature, which is capable of mitigating the consequences of natural causalities through planned and rational production and reproduction.

Conclusion

We would like the facts and assumptions highlighted in this article to be invalid. But social theory, in a pandemic situation like the one we are dealing with today, cannot hide them because it analyses the Brazilian socio-historical reality, where minimum collective health conditions were not priorities in public policy agendas.

After presenting some repercussions of Covid-19 on social reproduction, we cannot but emphasize that social relations based on the production and accumulation of capital place giant limits on governments and states to make decisions that privilege life and human rights in the face of pandemics that severely affect the capitalist economy. For, even in normal times, public health is overlooked in the face of capitalist development.

The disgusting debate that opposed saving the “economy” or saving life has had repercussions in all parts of the world, an expression of the capitalist economic rationality personified by some subjects. However, certain evidence is that the Covid-19 pandemic accelerated the capital crisis that was already underway, as it also evidenced that there is class struggle in contemporary history and that the sub-

altern classes are the most punished in these processes.

The world crisis we are experiencing in the year 2020 will be recorded in the annals of history, and, due to the very characteristics of the current economy, the consequences tend to be gigantic and unprecedented. According to Chesnais (n.d.), the Covid-19 pandemic is the consequence of capitalism’s relations with nature. This is an exogenous shock, since ‘world capitalism stands before a wall. It is being confronted by its social consequences, but also by the economic, global warming and dominant technologies.’ In the immediate future, countries will be dragged into deep recession, within a globalized and strongly hierarchical economy. The forecasts for the world economy, published in April 2020, considering the hypothesis of a decrease in the Covid-19 pandemic in the second half of the year, point, according to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), to a 3% contraction in world GDP and 11% in world trade. The World Trade Organization (WTO) is more pessimistic and foresees a decrease in world trade of up to 32% (Chesnais n.d.). These figures will be put to the test in the coming months. The certainty we already have is that poverty and job insecurity for the majority of the population are certain and constant. Perhaps the dream of Žižek (2020, 43) that, ‘the coronavirus also forces us to reinvent communism based on trust in people and science’, may still give us some hope.

Therefore, redirecting production relations together with the socially produced wealth by the productive forces of contemporary capitalism and, consequently, prioritizing public investment in unified international attention to the health of the population, even from a reforming perspective, ends up being the only way out in the short and medium term for humanity.

REFERENCES

Alencastro, L. F. (2000) *O Trato Dos Viventes: Formação Do Brasil No Atlântico Sul*. São Paulo: Companhia das Letras (In Portuguese).

Bambirra, Vania. (2013) *O Capitalismo Dependente Latino-Americano*. Florianópolis: Insular (In Portuguese).

Bihir, A. (2020) “França: Pela Socialização Do Aparato de Saúde.” In *Coronavírus e a Luta de Classes*, edited by M. Davis and et al. Brasil: Terra sem amos (In Portuguese).

Bombardi, L., and P. Nepomuceno. (2020) “Covid-19: Desigualdade Social e Tragédia No Brasil.” *Le Monde Diplomatique Brasil*, April 29, 2020 (In Portuguese). <https://diplomatique.org.br/covid-19-desigualdade-social-e-tragedia-no-brasil>.

Breilh, J. (2020) *Derterminación social de la salud. Hacia uma salud colectiva*. Interview by Punto de Partida. Interview. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wBT_NpB-vew&feature=youtu.be. (In Spanish).

Caixa Econômica Federal n.d. (2020) “Auxílio emergencial do Governo Federal.” Governmental webpage. Accessed May 7. <https://auxilio.caixa.gov.br/inicio>. (In Portuguese)

Chesnais, François n.d. (2020) *Capitalismo está diante de uma parede* Interview by Tutameia. Accessed May 8. <https://tutameia.jor.br/capitalismo-esta-diante-de-uma-parede-diz-chesnais>. (In Portuguese).

Chuang n.d. (2020) “Social Contagion: Microbiological Class War in China.” *Chuang (blog)*. Accessed May 15. <http://chuangcn.org/2020/02/social-contagion/>. (In English).

Davis, Mike. (2020) “A crise do coronavírus é um monstro alimentado pelo capitalismo.” In *Coronavírus e a luta de classes*, edited by Mike Davis, Alain Badiou, Alain Bihir, Raul Zibech, and Slavoj Žižek. Brasil: Terra sem amos. (In Portuguese).

FOLHAPRESS. (2020) “Mais de 11 Milhões No Brasil Moram Em Casas Superlotadas.” *O Tempo*, March. <https://www.otempo.com.br/brasil/mais-de-11-milhoes-no-brasil-moram-em-casas-superlotadas-1.2317766>. (In Portuguese).

Foster, John Bellamy. (2020) *Capitalismo de catástrofe: mudança climática, COVID-19 e crise econômica* Interview by Farooque Chowdhury. <https://envolverde.cartacapital.com.br/capitalismo-de-catastrofe-mudanca-climatica-covid-19-e-crise-economica/>. (In Portuguese).

Harvey, David. (2020) “Política Anticapitalista Em Tempos de COVID-19.” In *Coronavírus e a Luta de Classes*, edited by M. Davis and et al. Brasil: Terra sem amos. (In Portuguese).

IBGE. (2020) “Pesquisa Nacional Por Amostra de Domicílios Contínua - PNAD Contínua.” Statistics. PNAD Contínua. Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística. <https://www.ibge.gov.br/estatisticas/sociais/trabalho/17270-pnad-continua.html?edicao=27258&t=sobre>. (In Portuguese).

Kitahara, Akemi. (2020) “Informalidade Cai, Mas Atinge 38 Milhões de Brasileiros.” Agência Brasil, April 1. <https://agenciabrasil.ebc.com.br/economia/noticia/2020-03/informalidade-cai-mas-atinge-38-milhoes-de-trabalhadores>. (In Portuguese).

Lukács, György.(2009) “As Bases Ontológicas Do Pensamento e Da Atividade Do Homem. [The Ontological Bases of Man’s Thought and Activity].” In *O Jovem Marx e*

Outros Escritos de Filosofia [The Young Marx and Other Philosophical Writings], 225–45. Rio de Janeiro: Editora da UFRJ. (In Portuguese).

Para Uma Ontologia Do Ser Social II. (2013) São Paulo: Boitempo. (In Portuguese).

Marx, Karl. (2010) *Manuscrisos Econômico-Filosóficos.* São Paulo: Boitempo. (In Portuguese).

Grundrisse: Manuscritos Econômicos de 1857-1858: Esboços Da Crítica Da Economia Política [Grundrisse: Economic Manuscripts of 1857-1858: Drafts of the Critique of Political Economy] (2011) São Paulo: Boitempo. (In Portuguese).

Moura, Julia. (2020). “Pico de Covid-19 Nas Classes Altas Já Passou; o Desafio é Que o Brasil Tem Muita Favela, Diz Presidente Da XP.” *Folha de S. Paulo*, May 5. <https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/mercado/2020/05/brasil-esta-indo-bem-no-controle-do-coronavirus-e-pico-nas-classes-altas-ja-passou-diz-presidente-da-xp.shtml>. (In Portuguese).

OPAS, and OMS. (2020) “COVID-19 (Doença Causada Pelo Novo Coronavírus).” Institutional. *Folha Informativa.* https://www.paho.org/bra/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=6101:covid19&Itemid=875. (In Portuguese).

Paim, Cynthia Schuck, and Wladimir J. Alonso. (2020) *Pandemias, Saúde Global e Escolhas Pessoais.* Alfenas: Cria. (In Portuguese).

RBA. (2020) “Coronavírus Pode Ter Surgido Do Modelo Predatório Do Agronegócio, Diz Estudo.” *Rede Brasil Atual* (blog). April 2. <https://www.redebrasilatual.com.br/ambiente/2020/04/coronavirus-agronegocio-modelo-predatorio>. (In Portuguese).

Sakamoto, Leonardo. (2020) “Covid-19: Dois Trabalhadores Bolivianos de Oficinas de Costura Morrem Em SP.” *UOL*, April 8. <https://noticias.uol.com.br/colunas/leonardo-sakamoto/2020/04/08/covid-19-dois-trabalhadores-bolivianos-de-oficinas-de-costura-morrem-em-sp.htm?cmpid=>. (In Portuguese).

Silveira, Daniel. (2020). “Cerca de 18,4 milhões de brasileiros não recebem água encanada diariamente, aponta IBGE.” *G1*, May 6. <https://g1.globo.com/economia/noticia/2020/05/06/cerca-de-184-milhoes-de-brasileiros-nao-recebem-agua-encanada-diariamente-aponta-ibge.ghtml>. (In Portuguese).

Vendramini, Celia, and Soraya Franzoni Conde. (2020). “Vítimas Do Coronavírus: A Classe Trabalhadora Imigrante.” *Desacato*, April 30, sec. A Outra Reflexão. <http://desacato.info/vitimas-do-coronavirus-a-classe-trabalhadora-imigrante-por-celia-vendramini-e-soraya-franzoni-conde/>. (In Portuguese).

Vespa, Talyta. (2020) “Em Vez Da Idade, Classe Social Passa a Definir Quem Morre de Covid No País.” *UOL*, May 6, 2020. <https://noticias.uol.com.br/saude/ultimas-noticias/redacao/2020/05/06/no-brasil-covid-19-nao-mata-por-idade-mas-por-endereco-sugere-estudo.htm>. (In Portuguese).

Wallace, R. (2016) *Big Farms Make Big Flu: Dispatches on Infectious Disease, Agribusiness, and the Nature of Science.* New York: Montly Review Press. (In English)

Žižek, Slavoj. (2020) “Um Golpe Como ‘Kill Bill’ No Capitalismo.” In *Coronavírus e a Luta de Classes*, edited by M. Davis and et al. Brasil: Terra sem amos. (In Portuguese)